

**USE OF ADVANTAN FOR THE EXTERNAL TREATMENT OF
ALLERGIES AND INFLAMMATORY DERMATOSES.**

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Abstract: There are relatively few revolutionary inventions in dermatology that treat some skin diseases at least in magnitude. The introduction of topical steroids in the complex treatment of inflammatory and allergic dermatoses is exactly what this effect is.

Key words: Allergy, inflammation, treatment, advantan, dermatosis.

Аннотация: В дерматологии относительно немного революционных изобретений, которые лечат некоторые кожные заболевания хотя бы по масштабу. Введение топических стероидов в комплексное лечение воспалительных и аллергических дерматозов — это как раз то, что представляет собой этот эффект.

Ключевые слова: Аллергия, воспаление, лечение, адвантан, дерматоз.

For the first time in the early 1950s, the treatment of topical steroids in clinical practice is strengthening the position of treatment in the treatment of the most common dermatoses. These diseases have a very strong complex effect on various stages of the pathogenesis of skin diseases characterized by diseases, proliferation,

disease manifestations, peeling, etc. It is explained by the metabolic effect of glucocorticosteroid hormones (GCSH) when applied locally:

- production of prostaglandins, leukotrienes, thromboxanes by blocking the activity of GCSH phospholipase A2;
- GCSH inhibits the synthesis of glycosaminoglycans, collagen and elastin, the release of histamine and other anti-inflammatory mediators, the release of mast cells, the appearance of Langerhans;
- immunocompetent cells inhibit the synthesis of nucleic acids (primary DNA) in basal and fibroblasts of the epidermis.

There is a wide range of vision for the use of topical glucocorticosteroids in the treatment of skin diseases in children and adults: seborrheic dermatitis, atopic dermatitis, various ways of hereditary and acquired erythroderma, eczema, hereditary bullous. epidermolysis, psoriasis, urticaria, lupus erythematosus, contact and allergic dermatitis and other allergic dermatoses.

Introduction: Corticosteroid drugs enter the skin through the stratum corneum of the epidermis, hair follicles, and skin glands. Moisturizing the skin increases its permeability to glucocorticosteroids 100 times. This is the free use of clothing, occlusive clothing.

There are about 50 corticosteroids available in the current pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan, which causes certain harm to the practitioner in the organization GKS enterprise for a specific patient. At the same time, you should be aware of the severity of the vasoconstrictor effect according to the European classification of the potential activity of corticosteroids with GCSH. Miller-Munro is divided into 4 classes: weak, moderately strong, strong and very strong. The therapeutic effect of

local GCSH depends on the correct determination of the dosage form, which determines the depth of penetration of the drug into the skin, the structure and concentration of the glucocorticoid in the drug. Glucocorticosteroid preparations in the form of ointments penetrate much better than cream. The scalp, facial skin, and oil-based lotions, films, or aerosols respond to loading. Thus, the degree of penetration of GCSH into the lesion is maximal in the case of steroid ointment, small when applying the cream, and small when GCSH is removed from its own lotion (solution).

In chronic dermatosis, with dryness, peeling, lichenification, from ointments recommended to start. In acute processes with edema, vesiculation, weeping, lotions, aerosols and creams are preferred. It is recommended to use non-oily lotions, aerosols, and gels on the scalp, face, and skin folds. In highly infiltrating processes, the concentration of the drug and the depth of penetration into the skin can be monitored using HCSG using a compressive needle (under occlusion). Combined with the activity of local steroids and significantly reduces the overall side effects. Changes in local side effects and systemic side effects depend on absorption of GCSH into the systemic correction.

Local side effects include atrophy, persistent melting telangiectasias, papules and pustules, steroid acne, atrophic skin lines, hypertrichosis, pigmentation changes and rarely external contact sensitivity. In addition, there may be a slowdown in erosion and wound healing.

Common side effects include Cushingoid, dwarfism, steroid diabetes, increased protein catabolism, electrolytes, hypertension, and osteoporosis. Common Addison's property (stone-notes, anorexia, orthostatic hypotension, vascular

collapse) with topical GCSH interest.

The frequency and severity of side effects are related to the use of HCSG in areas, injuries, injuries, diaper rash, "sensitive" highway (axilla, inguinal folds, scrotum) and especially when using occlusive dressings. said. , adding strong keratolytics. The frequency of side effects caused by the occurrence of the "parents" syndrome in young and adult patients, especially the long and irrational use of topical steroids, especially in pediatric practice.

It can be used when the expected benefit from the treatment of local GCSH is higher than the management of GCSH or when it comes to vital indicators for the appointment of glucocorticoid hormones.

GISukolin et al., 2004 agree.

"halogen-containing glucocorticosteroids - alclometasone and mometasone (containing chlorine), clobetasol, triamcinolone, fluticasone, fluocinolone. acetamide, betamethasone (containing fluorine) are not used for a long time. for elimination or treatment with slightly stronger corticosteroids to help, for reactions to the treatment of "old" infiltrates, recommendations for localization in places: face, large fold, genitals.

Thus, when cleaning corticosteroids, the tool is highly effective and follows the most effective tool. These requirements are largely met by the non-halogenated topical corticosteroid ADVANT (0.1% methylprednisolone). asonate). It belongs to the class of drugs with strong effects. Advantan differs from other topical steroids, because in its case, the structure C17 and C21 position with double esterification improves lipophilicity, and the ball in the affected accumulation, the preparation in

the dermis; The methyl group in the C6 position helps to increase the high activity of the drug and restore it once a day due to the binding strength of the receptor in the inflammatory site; The absence of fluorine or chlorine atoms at the C6, C9, or C21 positions does not slow natural inactivation. vehicles in the form of glue, vehicles do not reduce the strength of the connection with transcor, showing systemic side effects.

Advantan by Schering (Germany) 4 dosing, manufacturing

Release: emulsified, cream, ointment, ointment, buteri, depending on the nature of the disease and the nature of the process. The first three dosage forms of Advantan are registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan and are available on the pharmaceutical market).

Since "advantan emulsion" is an "oil-in-water" suspension (water content 67.55%), it does not directly contribute to the evaporation of water and helps inflamed skin disease. , of the face and face, on the sheet with hair.

Advantan cream is an oil-water emulsion, but the water content is 0% and is prescribed in the acute (non-wetting) and subacute stages of recovery.

Advantan ointment is a water-in-oil emulsion with a water content of 30%, more for the irrigation process with strong strong infiltration and itching. At the same time, the steam of the aid to the ointment is shown, which helps to loosen the cornea and improves the penetration of the hormone into the location of the dermis.

The dosage form of Advantan "oily ointment" is water-repellent, has an occlusive effect on the skin, promotes strong relaxation of the epidermis and penetration of glucocorticoids into the dermis. "Advantan" oily ointment is prescribed for diseases with symptoms of hyperkeratosis, lichenification, peeling.

Being a diester, Advantan has optimal lipophilicity and ensures rapid penetration of the steroid into the skin. After penetrating the skin, MPA is hydrolyzed to methylprednisolone-17-propionate, a metabolite with a high affinity for skin steroid receptors (6 times higher than hydrocortisone). making, bioactivation process methylprednisolone is more active on inflamed skin. It is the high affinity of methylprednisolone for steroid receptors that allows the long-term therapeutic effect of acepotate advantan and its administration 1 time per day. Methylpredzolon-17-propionate is very quickly inactivated, conjugated with glucuronic acid and excreted from the body, which increases the systemic side effects of the physical organism. There are observations that, even in widespread lesions, the application of 40 g of Advantan ointment / cream for 8 days did not suppress endogenous glucocorticoid secretion in adults.

E. Ramp, in children with atopic dermatitis, moved that after a seven-day course of treatment with a lawyer, body collection affected up to 58%. suppression of corticosteroid production did not occur. According to JP Orton, treatment with Advantan does not cause treatment atrophy.

The purpose of the investigation: to guide the clinical development of different dosage measures (emulsion, cream, ointment) of Advantan in the complex treatment of children with atopic dermatitis and adults with atopic dermatitis, focal and diffuse neurodermatitis, seborrheic dermatitis. and seborrheic eczema, discoid lupus erythematosus.

Materials and methods: we observed 24 children (12 boys and 10 girls) aged 9 to 13 months and 94 adults (49 men and 45 women) aged 19 to 64 with a diagnosis of atopic dermatitis. Among the observed adults, atopic dermatitis was detected in 94

patients, focal neurodermatitis in 19 patients, diffuse neurodermatitis in 12 patients, discoid lupus erythematosus in 8 patients, seborrheic dermatitis in 13 patients, and seborrheic eczema in 10 patients. eczema - at 18.

Results and discussion: Children with atopic dermatitis received systematic treatment according to a clinical protocol for the diagnosis and treatment of this dermatosis; Advantan (emulsion, cream or ointment) is applied once a day to the affected surface. day the woman lasted from 14 to 23 days. In 3 out of 24 patients, the advanced course showed no signs of disease until clinical recovery, in the remaining 11 patients, or good recovery was noted, that is, 75-90% was obtained and no other damage was removed. Advantan treatment was well tolerated in all children.

Adult patients with atopic dermatitis, focal or diffuse neurodermatitis are prescribed traditional systemic treatment.

Current clinical protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of these dermatoses without the use of oral or parenteral corticosteroid hormones. External treatment was carried out once a day (often) with an emulsion or ointment at night, depending on the condition of the foci and the localization of the site. the average of the inspection. 2.5 weeks. However, 15 of 19 patients experienced clinical recovery or good improvement in adult patients with atopic dermatitis,

- in 2 patients and slight improvement - in 2 patients. Patients with focal or diffuse neurodermatitis (a total of 26 patients) achieved healthy remission in 11 patients, improvement in 8 patients, improvement in 7 patients.

Patients with discoid lupus erythematosus (8 people) received plaquenil 200 mg 2 times a day in 10-day courses with a 5-day break (a total of 2-3 courses), together

with nicotinic acid drugs, vitamin B 6 , A treatment. , E,

C. Advantan cream or ointment was administered once a day depending on the location and file status of the lupus lesions. Advantan for all 25-40 days of systemic treatment. On days 0-12 of treatment, fociemia and infiltrations decreased in high-grade courses, and by the end of treatment, hyperemia and follicular hyperkeratosis completely disappeared in all 8 patients, but foci residual atrophy. (from 2 to 7 years of the disease).

It was carried out with advantan in the form of emulsion or cream once a day for 9-10 days, then skinoren gel or cream was supported. Manifestations of seborrheic dermatitis may disappear immediately or completely by the end of the week.

Patients with seborrheic and true eczema have taken common diseases into production clinical protocols for the treatment of these patients. None of the patients received systemic treatment with GCSH. Stone therapy with advantan 1 time a day (usually disease) depending on the state of the disease and infiltration, emulsion, cream or ointment was carried out. It lasted from 16 to 22 days, only 2 now it lasted 28 days. at the death of the already stopped or does not remain at the level of its intensity; in the foci of eczema, vesiculation stopped, at the level of hyperemia and infiltration, there were no excoriations; psoriatic papules and the product turned pale, infiltration and desquamation did not subside. By the end of the course of the disease, clinical recovery was noted in 7 of 10 patients with seborrheic eczema and in 11 of 18 patients with true eczema. The remaining 10 patients show improvement.

Conclusion: Advantan treatment was well received by all young and old patients, no serious reactions were observed in any case. Our next corresponds well with the years of various authors from other countries.

Thus, Advantan can be recommended for the treatment of all clinical treatment of dermatosis, lupus erythematosus, neurodermatitis in adults and children.

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